

The LSST Transient and Variable Stars Science Collaboration Charter

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This document describes the governing and managing structure of the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) Transients and Variable Stars Science Collaboration (TVS SC, also referred to here as “the Collaboration”).

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Chairs role and responsibilities

The LSST TVS SC is governed by two *co-Chairs*. The co-Chairs are conveners and a conduit for communication: they communicate information from and to the LSST Project and Corporation from and to the TVS subgroups via the *subgroup*

Coordinators. They oversee the work of the TVS panels (see below) by making sure that the panels promptly address requests (but do not overwrite panels' decisions), they review and have final decision on proposals to create new subgroups and task forces, they review the proposed deliverables and timelines for new task forces and review the task forces' progress, they organize and preside over regular teleconferences which should be attended mandatorily by the subgroup Coordinators, and by other members as they wish (more detail is provided in the [Supplementary Material](#)).

The co-Chairs are also responsible for addressing requests and complaints of members of the Collaboration if they wish to communicate them directly to the chairs, instead of going through their subgroup coordinator, and for maintaining the common-use infrastructure like GitHub and the Collaboration website.

Benefits of Membership

By obtaining membership, the applicant acquires access to ways to communicate with other TVS members (access to the LSSTC slack, the community.lsst.org private channels, and the dissemination mailing list), access to any available Collaboration resources including data products, software, and developing resources if they exist, interact with the LSST Project members (starting with the Project-Collaboration liaisons), access to funding resources dedicated to the SCs when available, and support to apply for said resources.

Criteria for membership

Membership in the TVS SC, as in any other LSST Science Collaboration, is a privilege limited to the LSST data-rights holding community.

Upon applying for membership to TVS, individuals need to submit a statement about their expertise and their planned contribution over the 2 following years (through [this form](#)). This plan should be reviewed for feasibility by the TVS Membership Panel (see below), who may ask the applicant to revise it until they are satisfied. However, membership should generally be granted to most individuals that have LSST data

rights, even if the planned contribution is minimal, as initial membership is at the rank of *Associate*.

Once the new member has obtained access to the TVS information channels, the new member will be in a position to decide on her or his level of contribution and dedication, and adjust their membership accordingly possibly becoming *Full*, or *Core* member (see below for details of the rights and responsibilities associated to each membership level and paths to change membership level).

A condition for membership is the acknowledging and signing of the TVS SC Publication Policy and Code of Conduct.

Membership Tiers:

Full and Associate

Recognizing that members have a range of commitments that may change over time, and that members may contribute at different levels during this time, TVS recognizes two types of membership: *full* and *associate* member. Full membership reflects an ongoing, active contribution to the activities of one or more of the subgroups with which the member is affiliated. Associate members may have a casual participation in the life of the subgroup or TVS as a whole, and are encouraged to increase their involvement whenever they wish.

The *membership panel* (see below) can also grant full membership to a member that is participating and contributing to TVS overall through service activities to the Collaboration, although that person may not qualify to be a “full member” of her or his subgroups based on the level of activity within the subgroups.

Core

TVS SC *core* members are defined as TVS members who have made significant, extensive contributions to the TVS SC for at least two years. Core membership may be achieved via outstanding scientific contributions (but is not exclusive by this) that benefit and enable TVS members and LSST in general, by serving in any of the TVS Panels described below, as subgroup Coordinator, as lsst-stack support team, as spokesperson or in an outstandingly active role in a TVS SC task force, as defined by the task force itself. Core members have the right to be asked if they want to be

co-authors on TVS publications, as defined in [the LSST TVS Publication Policy \(currently under review\)](#). The LSST TVS Publication Policy defines the rights of core members to be on TVS publications, as well as the rights of the paper core authors to appeal a core member's participation.

Core member status is obtained through a process of nomination and confirmation. Any member may nominate any other eligible member to acquire core member status. Nominations for core member status can be submitted through [this form](#). The TVS membership panel (see below) will review the nomination and either approve or deny this award. If awarded, core membership shall be granted for a period of up to two years (as long as the member continues to hold LSST data rights) unless a specific request to remove core member status for an individual is submitted and upheld after review, and only in violations of the code of conduct, publication policies, or repeated abuses of the co-authorship privileges afforded by the status of TVS core member.

Core and full members can serve on the TVS SC panels (see below) and vote in the elections of chairs and panel members.

Subgroups

The Collaboration is comprised of a number of subgroups, 14 at the time of writing, representing different topics of scientific interest. Upon applying to become a TVS member, each applicant has to choose a primary subgroup affiliation and one or more subgroups. Full and core members may propose to start new subgroups, as discussed below.

Subgroup leadership

Each subgroup is led by at least one and no more than three *subgroup coordinators*. Subgroups without a coordinator, or where all coordinators are associate members, shall be considered “inactive”.

Members who wish to change their affiliations between subgroups should agree to this in advance with both their old and prospective subgroup coordinators.

The coordinators are the primary conduit of information between the Project and Corporation (through the Collaboration chairs) and the subgroup in both directions. They should organize regular (online) meetings to

- 1) assure the subgroup members are actively working to advance the scope of the subgroup, conduct scientific investigations and preparatory work for LSST,
- 2) communicate news and information regarding the Project to subgroup members in a timely fashion, and answer or relay to the co-Chairs any questions that arise,
- 3) monitor membership, including reviewing *full* and *associate* member status,
- 4) approve the affiliation of new members within the subgroup.

The cadence of the subgroup meetings, and the details of the media, are left to the subgroup leadership.

Each subgroup coordinator should regularly assess the level of membership of their primary and secondary members: “full” and “associate” members, reflecting respectively an on-going contribution to the subgroup activities, and a casual participation in the life of the subgroup. If someone’s membership level changes, both the member and the membership panel shall be notified promptly by the subgroup coordinator(s). The membership panel shall adjudicate any disputes over changes in membership status (see below). Coordinators are encouraged to contact in advance all members who may transition from full to associate membership in the near future, and to discuss their level of membership with them.

Task Forces

Task forces (TFs) are intra-subgroup temporary groups of members that actively pursue a specific time-sensitive goal within the Collaboration.

The scope and purpose of a TF should be

- Relevant to more than one subgroup,
- Have a well defined goal and set of deliverables,
- Be time-sensitive, and a timeline to achieve the proposed goal and deliverables should be established early on in the lifetime of the task force,
- Have a spokesperson, who will be the point of reference for communication with the TF, particularly for the Collaboration chairs to reach out to the TF, and
- May have a separate Chair, who assumes responsibility for coordinating the tasks to be carried out.

The set of deliverables and a timeline to achieve them (including a Gantt chart) should be delivered to the Collaboration chairs within a month of activation of the TF for approval, and the TF should set up a webpage (within lsst-tvs.github.io) to publicly declare their goals, deliverables, and a timeline to achieve them.

Panels

Three permanent panels shall support the work of the Collaboration as follows:

- A membership panel,
- A publication panel, and
- An ethics panel.

The **Membership Panel**

reviews new membership applications and status changes from associate to full or full to associate member (all new members have an initial status of associate) as communicated to the panel by the subgroup coordinators or the chairs. New applications should be approved by both the membership panel and by the coordinator(s) of the primary subgroup chosen by the applicant in a timely manner (see [Supplementary Material](#)). Secondary affiliations need only to be approved by the respective subgroup coordinator(s).

When core member nominations are received, the membership panel will review and confirm or deny these nominations within a month.

The timeline for these reviews is defined in the [Supplementary Material](#).

The membership and publication panels should have at least 3 members, chosen through a full-members-wide election. Details on the elections follow below. Only full and core members of the Collaboration qualify to serve on the TVS SC panels.

The **Publication Panel**

reviews TVS SC publications to assure that they comply with the [TVS publication rules](#) and that they are quality publications, and reviews appeals to the publication

co-authorship requests according to our [Publication Policy](#). The timeline for this review is defined in the [Publication Policy](#) document

The **Ethics Panel**

described in the [TVS Code of Conduct](#), is responsible for listening to concerns and complaints about violation of the Code of Conduct while maintaining confidentiality. This panel is composed of at least 2 TVS members at all times. The panel must be gender diverse and it is advised that its members are at a different seniority levels whenever the candidates pull allows it, to assure that all members of the collaboration can be comfortable reporting their concerns. The Ethics Panel is elected by all TVS SC full members and it rotates every two years, with a one year offset between the two panel members.

Policy Review Panel

In addition to these standing panels, the co-Chairs may opt to create a temporary **Policy Review Panel** whenever necessary to review proposals to modify the TVS charter and policies.

LSST-stack support team

Members of TVS that are knowledgeable and willing to help other TVS members on using any component of the LSST stack (including but not limited to MAF, OpSim, CatSim, PhoSim, Science Pipelines, and Science Platform) can serve in the “lsst-stack support team”. In this role they should make themselves available to all TVS SC members to answer questions about the use of these pieces of software. By serving on the LSST-stack support team (for at least a year) TVS SC members can acquire full member status (subject to membership panel review of their contribution and approval). Applications to join the LSST-stack teams should be submitted by direct communication with the TVS co-Chairs.

Elections

Full and core members have the right to be nominated as candidates for, candidate themselves for, and vote in all TVS election including:

- 1) The election of co-Chairs (as needed),
- 2) The election of members for the Membership Panel (every year),
- 3) The election of members for the Publication Panel (every year),
- 4) The election of members for the Ethics Panel (every year),

Hereafter, the terms “yearly cycle” and “annual” should be understood as the academic year, from September 1st to August 31st.

All panel members can serve no more than three consecutive terms.

Proposing a new subgroup

New subgroups, as well as the merging of existing subgroups, should be proposed through [this form](#). A new subgroup can be proposed if:

- 1) The science scope that this subgroup would cover is not covered by any of the other subgroups.
- 2) A minimum of 5 members, including 2 full and/or core members of TVS are identified that have expertise and interests that are appropriate to a member of the new subgroup, and that have confirmed they want to be affiliated with the new subgroup (renouncing another subgroup membership if necessary to comply to the maximum of 4 affiliations within TVS)

The Collaboration co-Chairs shall review these proposals and decide whether the new subgroup can be formed. In the case of merging of subgroups, the chairs should discuss the proposal with the members and coordinators of both subgroups and listen to objections before making a final decision.

Proposing a new Task Force

New task forces should be proposed through [this form](#). A new task force can be proposed if:

- 1) The scope of the task force is relevant to more than one subgroup,
- 2) There is a time sensitive need of work to achieve the goals set forth by the TF

Please, make sure you read the [Supplementary Material](#)

The TVS SC organizational structure as of August 2018.

